

the Gospel according to Matthew

Matthew 19:1-12:

Marriage, Divorce, and 'Queers
of the Kingdom'

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The Gospel of Matthew, Chapter 19:1-12

(21st Century King James Version)¹

1 And it came to pass that when Jesus had finished these sayings, He departed from Galilee and came into the region of Judea beyond the Jordan.

2 And great multitudes followed Him, and He healed them there.

3 The Pharisees also came unto Him, testing Him and saying unto Him, “Is it lawful for a man to put away his wife for every cause?”

4 And He answered and said unto them, “Have ye not read, that He that made them at the beginning made them male and female,

5 and said, ‘For this cause shall a man leave father and mother and shall cleave to his wife, and the two shall be one flesh’?

6 Therefore they are no more two, but one flesh. What therefore God hath joined together, let not man put asunder.”

7 They said unto Him, “Why did Moses then command to give a writing of divorcement and to put her away?”

8 He said unto them, “Moses, because of the hardness of your hearts, suffered you to put away your wives, but from the beginning it was not so.

¹ The 21st Century King James Version (“KJ21”) was selected over other in order to maintain a theological balance, neither leaning too conservatively nor too liberally in its translation, whilst aligning with a holistic and inclusive approach, such as navigating matters of faith and belief of Christians on the margins and their principles and morals. Given the complexity and delicate nature of interpreting Matthew 19:1-12—a passage that deals with marriage, divorce, and sexual ethics—the KJ21 provides an updated yet traditionalist framework that might ultimately aid in a more in-depth exegesis. The formal tone and classical structure may help underscore the gravity of the issues being examined. (Although this “background paper” will form the foundation of an exegetical analysis of Matthew 19:1-12 in Greek language(s), the KJ21 will also be used as an invaluable tool in assisting with elucidating voids within existing exegetical scholarship as well as apprehending critical ascriptural reductionism.)

9 *And I say unto you, whosoever shall put away his wife, except it be for fornication, and shall marry another, committeth adultery; and whoso marrieth her who is put away doth commit adultery.”*

10 *His disciples said unto Him, “If the case of the man be so with his wife, it is not good to marry.”*

11 *But He said unto them, “All men cannot receive this saying, save they to whom it is given.*

12 *For there are some eunuchs who were so born from their mother’s womb, and there are some eunuchs who were made eunuchs by men, and there are eunuchs who have made themselves eunuchs for the Kingdom of Heaven’s sake. He that is able to receive it, let him receive it.”*

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Matthew 19:1-12: Marriage, Divorce, and 'Queers² of the Kingdom'

INTRODUCTION:

This paper provides a foundational analysis of a significant segment in Matthew's Gospel, specifically Chapter 19:1-12, as a precursor to a rigorous exegetical evaluation of its (most likely) original Greek text and intrinsic meaning.³ In this key passage, Jesus elucidates profound principles on love, marital unity, and human sexuality, extending the discourse to include eunuchs ("eunouchoi") and thereby broadening the conventional understanding of sexuality. Through an historical-critical lens, this investigation explores the text's multifarious background, encompassing factual, historical, religious, and socio-cultural contexts, to better understand Jesus' message of enduring love and genuine respect within intricate

² The term "Queer" has evolved from a pejorative label to an empowering academic and cultural concept, especially within the realms of queer studies and religious analysis. In these contexts, it serves as a critical lens for challenging traditional, binary views on gender and sexuality, aiming to unearth marginalized narratives in religious texts and practices. While its usage is geared towards fostering inclusivity and diversity in theological discussions, it is crucial to engage with LGBTQ+ communities and scholars for its respectful and nuanced application: Robert Goss, Deryn Guest, and Mona West, eds., *The Queer Bible Commentary* (London, England: SCM Press, 2015).

³ The majority scholarly consensus holds that the Gospel of Matthew was originally written in Greek. Several factors contribute to this view:

- (a) *Manuscript Evidence*: The earliest surviving manuscripts of Matthew are in Greek. No Aramaic or Hebrew manuscripts of this Gospel have been found that predate the Greek versions.
- (b) *Internal Evidence*: The Gospel itself contains Greek idioms and expressions that do not easily translate back into Aramaic or Hebrew, suggesting that Greek was the original language.
- (c) *Church Tradition*: Early Church Fathers like Eusebius claim that Matthew wrote his Gospel in Hebrew or Aramaic, but no such text has been found, and their accounts may reflect later traditions or misunderstandings.
- (d) *Audience*: The Gospel seems to target a Greek-speaking Jewish and Gentile Christian audience, familiar with the Septuagint (the Greek Old Testament), which aligns more closely with a Greek original.
- (e) *Literary Analysis*: The Gospel's structure, including its use of the Septuagint for Old Testament quotes, indicates a Greek origin.

See in particular R. T. France, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2007) and C. F. D. Moule, *Birth of the New Testament*, 3rd ed. (London: Continuum, 2000).

human relationships.⁴ The scope includes issues of divorce, celibacy, and marital commitment, accentuating the text's significance within its specific socio-cultural framework. However, the paper also acknowledges extant scholarly lacunae and challenges in authenticating the socio-historical reality surrounding Jesus. This becomes imperative for the preparation of an equitable and robust exegesis, especially as tradition has often supplanted authenticity in contemporary global perspectives.⁵

FACTS AND HISTORY:

Traditionally ascribed to Matthew, a tax collector and one of Jesus' apostolic circle, the Gospel of Matthew emerged anonymously, and its authorship appears not to be singular but rather communal.⁶ These texts emanated from nascent Christian communities endeavouring to codify the oral traditions and narratives concerning Jesus.⁷ Notably, philological evidence substantiates the text's original composition in Greek, later translated into Aramaic and Hebrew.⁸ While some scholars have posited

⁴ Such as the approach espoused by John J. Collins in his *Introduction to the Hebrew Bible: The Torah/Pentateuch*, 3rd ed. (Fortress Press, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1w6tbzp>.

⁵ Drawing parallels between Jean-Paul Sartre's existential critique of societal norms and the study of the historical Jesus, both endeavours grapple with the tension between tradition and authentic expression. In the realm of religious scholarship, this involves critically evaluating long-standing doctrines and interpretations to isolate the original teachings of historical figures like Jesus, much as Sartre argued for the liberation of individual identity from societal constraints. This quest for authenticity requires rigorous scrutiny, aiming to strip away layers of cultural and theological accretion that may distort the original message: John H. Gillespie, "Sartre and the Death of God," *Sartre Studies International* 22, no. 1 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.3167/ssi.2016.220104>; Jerome Gellman, "Jean Paul Sartre: The Mystical Atheist," *European Journal for Philosophy of Religion* 1, no. 2 (2009): 127–37, <https://doi.org/10.24204/ejpr.v1i2.344>.

⁶ Warren Carter, *Matthew and Empire: Initial Explorations* (London, England: Continuum International Publishing Group - Trinity, 2001); R. T. France, *The Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2007).

⁷ John Riches, ed., *The New Cambridge History of the Bible: From 1750 to the Present Volume 4* (Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 2015), <https://doi.org/10.1017/cho9780511842870>.

⁸ Mark Allan Powell, *Introducing the New Testament: A Historical, Literary, and Theological Survey*, 2nd ed. (Ada, OK: Baker Academic, 2018).

that a woman could have been the principal author, such considerations are tangential to this exposition.⁹

In juxtaposition, the Gospel's nuanced interplay between Judaic and Christian themes lends credence to the attribution of its authorship to Matthew, presumably during his lifetime. Its geographic genesis, generally thought to be Syria or Palestine, is embedded in a pedagogical milieu, predominantly among Jewish communities. Whether these were Messianic Jews or traditional Jews regarding Jesus' teachings as exegetical interpretations of their faith remains a subject of scholarly discord.¹⁰

Regarding its chronology, the Gospel is generally dated to the late first or early second century AD.¹¹ Multiple lines of evidence corroborate a late first-century dating: (1) The ecclesiastical landscape of AD 85, marked by the schism between the synagogue and the early Christian church; (2) The aftermath of the Roman sack of Jerusalem in AD 70 and temple annihilation in AD 87; and (3) The Gospel's ostensible dependency on the Gospel of Mark, which is commonly dated post 65-70 AD. Although some scholars have contested this last point, arguing that neither Jesus nor Matthew could have prophesied the Roman conflict, this viewpoint garners limited academic consensus.¹² Furthermore, the Gospel's apocalyptic

⁹ Thomas Bohache, "Matthew," in *The Queer Bible Commentary*, ed. Deryn Guest, Robert E. Goss, Mona West, Thomas Bohache (London, England: SCM Press, 2006), 487–516; Carol L. Meyers, Toni Craven, and Ross Shepard Kraemer, *Women in Scripture: A Dictionary of Named and Unnamed Women in the Hebrew Bible, the Apocryphal/Deuterocanonical Books, and the New Testament*, ed. Carol L. Meyers, Ross S. Kraemer, and Toni Craven (Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin (Trade), 2000); Angel Santiago-Vendrell, "The Gospel in a New Tune! The Appropriation of Ada María Isasi-Díaz's 'Historical Project' by Latina Pentecostals in the Formulation of a Theology of Evangelism," *Feminist Theology* 19, no. 1 (2010): 73–85, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0966735010372169>.

¹⁰ F. A. March and W. B. Owen, *The Ecclesiastical History of Eusebius* (Charleston, SC: BiblioLife, 2009); March & Owen, "Eusebius"; Ian Boxhall, "Matthew," in *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century*, ed. John J. Collins, Gina Hens-Piazza, Barbara Reid OP, and Donald Senior CP (London: T&T Clark, 2022), 1168–1237; Columbia University, "Historical Context for Matthew," Columbia.edu, accessed August 25, 2023, <http://www.college.columbia.edu/core/content/matthew/context>.

¹¹ Carter, *Matthew & Empire*; Powell, *Intro to NT*.

¹² Boxhall, *Matthew*; W. D. Davies and Dale C. Allison Jr, *Matthew 19-28: A Commentary* (London, England: T. & T. Clark, 1997); France, *The Gospel*; Robert Horton Gundry, *Matthew: A Commentary on His Handbook for a Mixed Church under Persecution*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1959); David Guzik, "Enduring Word Bible Commentary Matthew Chapter 19," *Enduring Word*, December 9,

terminology concerning the temple is only marginally more explicit than that of Mark.¹³ In light of Matthew's ministry within territories under the aegis of Roman dominion, it is unsurprising that theological exegesis frequently employs Roman imperial contexts as hermeneutical keys to interpretive insight.¹⁴

SOCIO-CULTURAL CONTEXT:

Within the historical framework of Matthew 19:1-12, it is also vital to consider the intermingling of Greco-Roman and Jewish cultures in Roman-ruled Judaea where these teachings were ostensibly disseminated. Greco-Roman traditions significantly influenced the sociocultural landscape, permeating diverse aspects such as law, governance, and social norms, including marital and sexual relationships. Set against the socio-cultural tapestry of Matthew 19:1-12; a tableau tinged with Greco-Roman marital ideologies, eunuchism, Roman legalism, and Jewish customs; it becomes imperative to scrutinise the *specific* Judaism of the epoch.¹⁵ Jesus' exhortation on the sanctity of matrimony and his nuanced stance on divorce find

2015, <http://enduringword.com/bible-commentary/matthew-19/>; Matthew Henry, "Commentary on Matthew 19 by Matthew Henry," *Blue Letter Bible*, March 1, 1996, http://www.blueletterbible.org/Comm/mhc/Mat/Mat_019.cfm; C. Keener, *Gospel of Matthew: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2009); Craig S. Keener, *Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1999); Right. Rev. W. Walsham How (Bishop of Wakefield), *The New Testament of Our Lord Jesus Christ: According to the Authorised Version, With a Brief Commentary by Various Authors* (London, England: Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge, 1908); Randolph V. Tasker, *Gospel According to St. Matthew* (William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1962); "Gospel Doctrine: Matthew," *Gospeldoctrine.com*, accessed August 25, 2023, <http://gospeldoctrine.com-new-testament/Matthew/matthew-19>.

¹³ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Gundry, *Matthew*; Henry, *Commentary*.

While Matthew and Mark do share some apocalyptic elements, particularly concerning the destruction of the Temple in Jerusalem, it is worth noting that this is usually interpreted as a reflection of the anxieties and events of their times, rather than direct evidence for the dating of either Gospel.

¹⁴ Warren Carter, *Matthew and Empire: Initial Explorations* (London, England: Continuum International Publishing Group - Trinity, 2001); Keener, *Commentary*; Riches, *Cambridge History*.

¹⁵ David Edward Aune, *Prophecy in Early Christianity and the Ancient Mediterranean World* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1998); Daniel Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct: The Rise of Heterosexuality and the Invention of the Jewish Man* (Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1997); Guzik, *Enduring Word*; Daniel J. Harrington, *Collegeville Bible Commentary New Testament Volume 1: The Gospel According to Matthew* (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1971); Luz, *Studies in Matthew*.

themselves at a confluence - simultaneously intersecting with prevalent Greco-Roman norms and contemporary Jewish praxis.¹⁶ His appeal for enduring affection, mutual respect, and an expanded array of relational possibilities confronts both societal orthodoxy and established Rabbinic hermeneutics, offering a vision that transcends temporal human affairs.¹⁷

First-century Judaism prized matrimony and permitted divorce under specific conditions, encapsulated in the phrase “except for *porneia*” - a term that, despite variegated semantic interpretations over the centuries, generally connotes sexual infidelity or immoral conduct.¹⁸ The Pharisaic interrogation of Jesus on divorce illuminates existing schisms within Jewish legal interpretation, an issue explored further below.¹⁹

Matthew’s frequent allusions to Jewish rituals, traditions, and Messianic prophecies underscore his target audience: Jewish-Christians.²⁰ In Matthew 19:1-12, Jesus articulates a theology of marriage and celibacy that, while partially aligning with prevailing Jewish norms, also situates itself within the broader Greco-Roman

¹⁶ J. Andrew Overman, *Matthew’s Gospel and Formative Judaism: The Social World of the Matthean Community* (Minneapolis, MN: Augsburg Fortress, 1990); John Riches, ed., *The New Cambridge History of the Bible the New Cambridge History of the Bible: From 1750 to the Present Volume 4* (Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 2015), <https://doi.org/10.1017/cho9780511842870>; Randolph V. Tasker, *Gospel According to St. Matthew*; O. Wesley Allen Jr, *Matthew* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2013).

¹⁷ Bohache, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Goss, *Queer Bible*; Daniel A. Heminiak, *What the Bible Really Says about Homosexuality* (New Mexico: Alama Square Press, 2018).

¹⁸ Goss, *Queer Bible*; M. Maina And Nathan, “The Question of Divorce Based on 19:1-12: Did Jesus Legalize Divorce on Ground for Sexual Immorality?” *Edinburgh Journal of Sociology, Psychology and Religious Studies* 1, no. 1 (2021): 40–57.

¹⁹ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Gundry, *Matthew*; Meier, *A Marginal Jew: Volumes 3 & 4*.

²⁰ Bohache, *Matthew*; Boxhall, *Matthew*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; C. Keener, *Gospel of Matthew: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 2009); Craig S. Keener, *Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1999).

milieu.²¹ Here, Jesus expands the traditional Jewish understanding of sexuality to include eunuchs, thereby extending the spectrum of acceptable sexual identities.

Geographically situated in Roman-ruled Judaea, the cultural backdrop of these teachings would inevitably have been shaped by Roman law and tradition.²² Notably, Jesus recognises the fluid spectrum of sexual relationships present in Greco-Roman society without overt condemnation.²³ Even though it could be argued that Jesus does not extend the matrimonial framework to same-sex partnerships, his teachings in Matthew 19:12 display an evident ethos of inclusivity and

Two important points must be made with respect to Matthew 19:1-12, its socio-cultural backdrop, and the words of Jesus:

(1) By invoking eunuchs in his teachings, Jesus subtly engages with the Greco-Roman views on sexuality and social roles, challenging both the Jewish and Roman orthodoxies in a bid to articulate a more inclusive vision of human relationships;²⁴ and

(2) When Jesus discusses marriage and divorce, he does so with a cognizance of the multi-faceted sociocultural tapestry that his audience inhabited. This Greco-Roman backdrop does more than provide an historical setting; it actively engages with Jesus' teachings the challenge to understand them not as static, isolated dictums but as dialogic engagements with the complexities of his contemporaneous world.²⁵

²¹ Craig Price, *Biblical Exegesis of New Testament Greek: James* (Eugene, OR: Wipf & Stock, 2008).

²² Boxhall, Matthew; J. Andrew Overman, *Matthew's Gospel and Formative Judaism: The Social World of the Matthean Community* (Minneapolis, MN: Augsburg Fortress, 1990); Powell, *Introducing the NT*.

²³ Bohache, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Goss, *Queer Bible*; Heminiak, *What the Bible Really Says*.

²⁴ The concept of "eunuchism," which features prominently in Matthew 19:12, also bears the mark of Greco-Roman influence. In the Roman world, eunuchs often held significant social and political roles, serving as attendants in imperial courts or participating in religious rites, a stark contrast to their marginalised status within Jewish society: Goss, *Queer Bible*; Schanke, *Rituals*.

²⁵ Carter, *Matthew and Empire*; Riches, *Cambridge History*.

RELIGIOUS CONTEXT:

Matthew 19:1-12 encapsulates a multifaceted religious context, serving as a microcosm of the larger ideological and theological dialogues of the period. It presents Jesus as a figure who, while deeply respectful of his Jewish heritage, is not constrained by it, and instead engages in constructive theological dialogue that enriches and expands it.

Shammai and Hillel were two prominent schools of thought within Judaism during the Second Temple period.²⁶ The Pharisees were a religious group with various perspectives, but they generally held a strong influence on Jewish religious life.²⁷ Regarding divorce, Shammai advocated for a stricter interpretation of Old Testament scripture, allowing divorce only in cases of serious misconduct. Hillel took a more lenient stance, permitting divorce for various reasons.²⁸

In Matthew 19:1-12, Jesus cites Genesis 2:24 to accentuate the concept that marriage is not merely a social construct but a divine ordinance.²⁹ By evoking the foundational creation narrative, he embeds the institution of marriage within the very fabric of divine will.³⁰ Furthermore, Jesus' stringent position against divorce demonstrates a robust alignment with the Deuteronomic stipulations, yet with a nuanced approach.³¹ This particular layer of complexity unveils a continuity with Old

²⁶ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*.

²⁷ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Harrington, *Collegeville*.

²⁸ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Harrington, *Collegeville*.

²⁹ Jesus also cites Genesis 1:27 and 2:24 in Mark 10:2-12, and Luke 16:18, regarding God's creation of marriage.

³⁰ Genesis 1:27 and 2:24.

³¹ Daniel I. Block, *Deuteronomy* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2012); Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Randolph V. Tasker, *Gospel According to St. Matthew* (William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1962).

Testament tenets, especially with regard to the concept of “*uncleanness*” found in Deuteronomy 24:1-4.

In Matthew’s Gospel, Jesus’ teachings also illuminate a transformative understanding of gender roles and sexual ethics within the socio-religious framework. While firmly rooted in Jewish tradition, Jesus liberally interprets its constraints. For instance, his acknowledgment of infidelity as a permissible ground for divorce dispels the gender-specific limitations often imposed by patriarchal norms. This marks a significant departure from established rabbinic interpretations.³²

The discourse then advances to incorporate the figure of the “*eunuch*,” denoted by the term “*eunouchoi*” in the original text. Traditionally marginalised within both Jewish and Greco-Roman contexts for their inability or unwillingness to participate in procreative acts, eunuchs here find a place within the expansive theology of Jesus. The inclusion of eunuchs for the “sake of the Kingdom of Heaven” is not merely an act of social inclusion but rather serves as a theological reconfiguration of acceptable sexual identities.³³

As for the intended audience of Matthew’s Gospel, it is salient to note that this Gospel was likely composed for a community that was neither exclusively Jewish nor Gentile but a complex tapestry of both. The Gospel, therefore, synthesises Jesus’ revolutionary teachings with traditional Jewish law and Greco-Roman ideologies to address a highly pluralistic audience. Matthew negotiates between these varying landscapes, achieving a nuanced approach that attests to the complex religious

³² Block, *Deuteronomy*; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Price, *The New Testament in Greek*; Tasker, *Gospel According to St. Matthew*; Wineguard, *Until Death*.

³³ Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Goss, *Queer Bible*; Riches, *Cambridge Bible History*; Ragnhild Schanke, “Rituals and Same-Sex Unions,” ed. Patrick Digoix Marie and Festy, *Same-Sex Couples, Same-Sex Partnerships, and Homosexual Marriages: A Focus on Cross-National Differentials* 124 (2004): 273–92, <https://same-sex.web.ined.fr/WWW/04Doc124Ragnhild.pdf>; Ragnhild Schanke, “Were Homosexuals Included in the Concept: ‘Born Eunuchs’, in Matthew 19:12?” (University of Manchester, 2003); Willard M. Swartley, *Homosexuality: Biblical Interpretation and Moral Discernment* (Scottsdale, AZ: Herald Press, 2003); Gary Taylor, *Castration: An Abbreviated History of Western Manhood* (London, England: Routledge, 2002).

environment of the time. His work reflects an acute awareness of the multiple religious identities and theological nuances his narrative would have to navigate.

LITERARY CONTEXT:

Within the Gospel of Matthew, Chapter 19:1-12 does not exist in isolation; rather, it resides amidst an intricate matrix of theological and ethical teachings. While the Gospel seems to oscillate between biography and religious text, it must be acknowledged that it carefully chronicles the sayings, actions, and miraculous events of Jesus, offering a theologically nuanced portrait for its intended audience. When read sequentially, Matthew 19:1-12 becomes an integral episode within the broader ethical instruction of Jesus, encompassing themes such as anger, desire, the ethics of promise-making, retribution, and even the radical notion of love for one's enemies.³⁴

The framing of the Pharisees' inquiry and Jesus' subsequent teachings on the subjects of matrimony, divorce, and celibacy, offers an architectural emphasis that subtly reverberates throughout the Gospel. This dialectical interaction amplifies the central ethical tenets of Jesus' ministry, holding a mirror to the prevailing ethos of the Jewish Christian communities of the era.³⁵

Although the Gospel's authorship, dating, and geographic origination remain subjects of scholarly debate, its strategic composition is widely acknowledged as masterful. It serves as a repository of historical, socio-cultural, and theological information, adroitly weaving Old Testament allusions and prophecies into the

³⁴ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Harrington, *Collegetown*.

³⁵ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Harrington, *Collegetown*.

narrative fabric.³⁶ Understanding the Gospel's intricate literary layout is instrumental in comprehending how Matthew 19:1-12 resonates with overarching themes and teachings.³⁷

Matthew's Gospel employs a blend of narrative storytelling and theological rhetoric. Its oratorical structure is particularly evocative; for instance, Jesus' interrogative methodology in the Gospel is seldom designed for *yes-or-no* answers. Instead, the queries often serve as pedagogical prompts, catalysing deeper contemplation and analytical reasoning among both his immediate audience and generations of subsequent readers.³⁸

LITERARY THEMATICS:

Matthew's Gospel encompasses various thematic sections, including the Sermon on the Mount, parables, discipleship lessons, and the Passion of the Christ, collectively weaving a narrative of Jesus' teachings, miracles, and interactions. Notably, the core teachings, such as the Beatitudes, Love for Enemies, and *Law of Fulfillment*, are presented in the Sermon on the Mount.³⁹ This Gospel also chronicles Jesus' journey to Jerusalem, Crucifixion, and Resurrection, combining his speeches

³⁶ Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Gundry, *Matthew*; Overman, *Matthew's Bible*. David; Guzik, "Enduring Word Bible Commentary Matthew Chapter 19," *Enduring Word*, December 9, 2015, <http://enduringword.com/bible-commentary/matthew-19/>; Harrington, *Collegeville*.

³⁷ Guzik, *Enduring Word*.

³⁸ Kurt Aland and Barbara Aland, *The Text of the New Testament: An Introduction to the Critical Editions and to the Theory and Practice of Modern Textual Criticism* (Leiden, Netherlands: Brill, 1987); Dami et al., Jesus Questions; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Matricciani & Caro, *Deep Language*; Zummy Anselmus Dami, Ferdinand Alexander, and Yanjumseby Yeverson Manafe, "Jesus' Questions in the Gospel of Matthew: Promoting Critical Thinking Skills," *Christian Education Journal Research on Educational Ministry* 18, no. 1 (2021): 89–111, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739891320971295>; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Emilio Matricciani and Liberato Caro, "A Deep-Language Mathematical Analysis of Gospels, Acts and Revelation," *Religions* 10, no. 4 (2019): 257, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel10040257>.

³⁹ Jerome, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*; Powell; *Intro. to NT*.

into a cohesive narrative.⁴⁰ Utilising diverse literary techniques, it highlights prophecy fulfillment, draws connections between the Old and New Testaments, and employs parables to impart spiritual and moral insights, particularly about the Heavenly Kingdom and ethics.⁴¹

The Gospel's symmetrical structure, evident through chiasmic patterns, further enhances its thematic coherence.⁴² References to God's presence at the beginning and end underscore His connection with humanity. Matthew's Gospel ultimately delivers Jesus' teachings on justice and the Kingdom of Heaven, prominently centred around the Sermon on the Mount.⁴³

The purity and permanence of marriage, celibacy for the Kingdom of Heaven, and (arguably⁴⁴) acceptance of diverse sexual orientations are all discussed in Matthew's Chapter 19:1-12. Jesus underlines the divine desire for marriage to be a lifetime commitment and that divorce is only allowed for sexual immorality. He encourages celibacy for some and acknowledges eunuchs, which may imply his acceptance of varying sexual orientation.⁴⁵

⁴⁰ Aland & Aland, *The Text of NT*; France, *The Gospel*.

⁴¹ William Foxwell Albright and C. S. Mann, *Matthew* (New York, NY: Bantam Doubleday Dell, 1995); David Edward Aune, *Prophecy in Early Christianity and the Ancient Mediterranean World* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B Eerdmans Publishing, 1998).

⁴² Matricciani & Caro, *Deep Language*.

⁴³ Boxhall, *Matthew*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; France, *The Gospel*, Powell, *Intro to NT*.

⁴⁴ To be discussed further below.

⁴⁵ Competing views are noted across a wide spectrum of commentaries, including: BlueLetterBible.org, "Biblical Scholarship," Accessed August 25, 2023. <http://www.blueletterbible.org>; Bohache, *Matthew*; Brooten, *Love Between Woman*; Davies & Allison, *Matthew*; Margaret A. Farley, *Just Love: A Framework for Christian Sexual Ethics* (Continuum International Publishing Group, 2008); France, *The Gospel*; Frederick J. Gaiser, "A New Word on Homosexuality? Isaiah 51:1-8 as a Case Study," *Word and World* 14, no. 3 (1994): 280–93; Goss, *Queer Bible*; Guzik, *Enduring Word*; Scott W. Hahn and Curtis Mitch, *Ignatius Catholic Study Bible: Matthew*, 2nd ed. (San Francisco, CA: Ignatius Press, 2011); Harrington, *Collegeville*; Henry, *Commentary*; M. Hietanen, "The Argumentation in Galatians," *Acta Theologica* 28, no. 2 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.4314/actat.v28i2.52342>; Columbia Uni, *Historical Context*; H. Wayne House, ed., *Divorce and Remarriage: Finding Guidance for Personal Decisions* (Downers Grove, IL: Inter-Varsity Press, 2000); Waldemar Janzen, *Exodus: Believers Church Bible Commentary* (Herald Press, 2000); Jennings, *Man Jesus Loved*; Keener, *Gospel*; Keener, *Commentary*; Loader,

Perceived incongruities in Matthew's narrative arise from scholars discerning deliberate distinctions. The Gospel contrasts the contemporary Jewish community's limitations, infighting, and outdated structures with the aspirations and beliefs of the Old Testament Israel.⁴⁶ Matthew clearly depicts this vibrant society relying on scribal authority, centring around the temple and its rituals and hesitating to fully embrace Jesus' proclamation of the Kingdom of Heaven.⁴⁷ This portrayal skilfully captures the emergence of a fervent, scripturally rooted community (which included the recognition of Abraham (homologous to Paul in Romans 4)), which, while embracing Jesus' profound teachings, acknowledges the need for reform and progress beyond its own confines.⁴⁸ Indeed, Matthew's Gospel seems to disallow surface-reading, and prompts inquiry into many different facets of religiosity and theology, and clearly was intended to prompt humanity to consider God's design and the future of human connections, setting the stage for a richer, subsequent exegetical analysis.

QUEERS OF THE KINGDOM?

In contemporary discourse, the teachings of Jesus in Matthew 19:1-12 can be viewed as a radical challenge to conventional perspectives on sexuality and

Sexuality & Jesus; Luz, *Studies in Matthew*; Meyers, *Women in Scripture*; Miller, *Hidden Gospel*; Maina, *Jesus & Divorce*; Nolland, *The Gospel*, Price, *Bible in Greek*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Schanke, *Homosexuals & Eunuchs*; Wineguard, *Until Death*.

⁴⁶ Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Robert Govett, *The Jews, the Gentiles, and the Church of God in the Gospel of Matthew the Jews, the Gentiles, and the Church of God in the Gospel of Matthew* (Legare Street Press, 2021); Lester L. Grabbe, *An Introduction to First Century Judaism: Jewish Religion and History in the Second Temple Period* (Self-Published [Amazon], 1998); Meier, *A Marginal Jew*, Vols. 1, 2, 3, & 4.

⁴⁷ Paula Fredriksen, *When Christians Were Jews: The First Generation* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2019); David Flusser, *Judaism and the Origins of Christianity* (Hebrew University Magnes Press, 2011).

⁴⁸ Fredrickson, *Christians/Jews*; Flusser, *Judaism/Christianity*. Also note Matthew's links to Abraham, as per Romans 4: Edward Adams, "Abraham's Faith and Gentile Disobedience: Textual Links between Romans 1 and 4," *Journal for the Study of the New Testament* 19, no. 65 (1997): 47–66, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0142064x9701906503>; D. A. Carson, Peter T. O'Brien, and Mark A. Seifrid, eds., *Justification and Variegated Nomism / Justification and Variegated Nomism: The Complexities of Second Temple Judaism* (Germany: Mohr Siebeck, 2001).

relationships. This assertion is rooted in historical-critical methodology, which emphasises the comprehension of texts within their socio-cultural milieu. By this method, scholars such as John J. Collins have illustrated the importance of unpacking cultural paradigms to grasp the text's meaning adequately.⁴⁹

In discussions on the New Testament, the subject of “*eunouchoi*” or eunuchs often becomes relegated to the periphery. Yet, the term “*eunouchoi*” is a multi-faceted one, employed 53 times across the Septuagint and the New Testament, pointing to various forms of sexual non-conformity.⁵⁰ When Jesus discusses three distinct categories of eunuchs in Matthew 19:12, he broadens the concept from mere physical conditions to include metaphorical implications about spiritual devotion and life choices.⁵¹

The audacity of Jesus' teachings on eunuchs becomes clearer when contextualised within the societal norms of the Hellenistic world. For example, Sarah Ruden discusses how sexual minorities, such as eunuchs, were marginalised in Greek and Roman societies. Jesus, by associating them with the Kingdom of God, turns these existing paradigms on their head, aligning divine love with social non-conformity.⁵²

Historical evidence suggests that early Judaism did not universally stigmatise sexual minorities or those who would be categorised as “*eunouchoi*.” Boyarin elucidated that Judaism maintained a nuanced view on male intimacy, as indicated

⁴⁹ John J. Collins, *A Study Companion to Introduction to the Hebrew Bible*, 2nd ed. (Fortress Press, 2014).

⁵⁰ Bohache, *Matthew*; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Loader, *Sexuality/Jesus*; Price, *Greek Bible*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Schanke, *Homosexuals/Eunuchs*.

⁵¹ Goss, *Queer Bible*; Loader, *Sexuality/Jesus*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Schanke, *Homosexuals/Eunuchs*.

⁵² Sarah Ruden, *Paul among the People: The Apostle Reinterpreted and Reimagined in His Own Time* (New York, NY: Image Books, 2011). This view is also reflected in: Bohache, *Matthew*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Schanke, *Homosexuals/Jesus*.

by the Talmud and Midrashic literature.⁵³ This complexity becomes crucial when interpreting Jesus' challenge to "*ho dynamenos kjorein, kjoreito*" ("*He who is able to accept this, accept it!*"). This appears to be a direct call to inclusivity, urging followers to adapt their rigid social norms in favour of a broader divine ethic.⁵⁴

CONCLUSION:

In summary, Matthew 19:1-12 stands as a multi-dimensional text that navigates complex issues of theology, ethics, and humanity. The passage's historical setting in first-century Palestine, its literary context within the Gospel of Matthew, and its socio-cultural backdrop enrich our comprehension. By critically examining these facets, including the impactful term "*eunouchoi*," we can better appreciate how Jesus disrupts established traditions, urging a broader, more inclusive understanding of love and human connection. Moreover, the religious influences from Judaism and the then-prevailing Hellenistic norms add layers to the discourse. The complex interactions between these contexts not only deepen our understanding of marriage and celibacy but also extend our appreciation of sexual diversity within the framework of Matthean ethics. In this quest for comprehension, we find ourselves at the intersection of tradition and authenticity. Our scholarly exploration serves as a conduit for re-evaluating human relationships in today's world, requiring not just intellectual scrutiny but also a readiness to reform our ethical frameworks and social paradigms.

⁵³ Daniel Boyarin, *Carnal Israel: Reading Sex in Talmudic Culture* (Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1995).

⁵⁴ Bohache, *Matthew*; Boyarin, *Unheroic Conduct*; Goss, *Queer Bible*; Heminiak, *What the Bible Really Says*; Loader, *Sexuality/Jesus*; Price, *Greek Bible*; Schanke, *Rituals*; Schanke, *Homosexuals/Eunuchs*.

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<https://smcl.bibliocommons.com/v2/record/S76C2680661>

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Accessed September 1, 2023,

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Page 28:

Jesus at Matthew 19:13-15 (immediately after the “eunuchoi” pronouncement):

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